

Ethno-Religious Minorities and Electoral Politics in Iran

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The electoral politics of post-revolutionary Iran are often portrayed in Western media and academic analyses as an enduring battle between reform-oriented pragmatism and varying shades of conservatism (Axworthy 2013; Amanat 2017; Hashemi and Postel 2011). An underexplored aspect that enhances our understanding of the complexities of Iranian politics is the extent of participation by ethnic and religious minority groups in its electoral processes. This intervention aims to advance understanding of political participation of ethnic and religious minorities and their place in the electoral system in Iran. Precise census data pertaining to ethnic and/or religious identification is not available, and is a politically sensitive issue, thus requiring a certain degree of extrapolation from known populations and their geographic location. As such, the primary focus will be on presiden-

tial election turnout in three provinces namely Sistan and Baluchistan, Kurdistan, and West Azerbaijan which contain populations that are commonly understood to be largely distinct in both ethnic and religious terms from the Persian and Shi'i majority in the country.¹

Exploring ethno-religious groups in Iran

Though often perceived to be centred around a Persian-speaking and, since the 16th Century, Shi'i, 'core,' ethnic and religious minority groups have a long history of political activism in Iran. Whether contributing to revolutionary activities, campaigning for minority rights, or being instrumentalised by external powers, minorities have played a significant role in Iran's political history. Noted works in the English language (Elling, 2013; Tohidi,

¹ We make use of field interviews in Iran, and the data provided by Mehrzad Boroujerdi's 'Iran Data Portal' at Syracuse University, which offers translations of key Iranian Ministry of Information statistics on elections, alongside other socio-economic and political data from Iran. <https://irandataportal.syr.edu/>

2009; Sanasarian, 2000) have sought to explore the broader historical and social contexts of ethnic and religious minorities in Iran, including in the Islamic Republic Era. Meanwhile, the US policy community has exhibited a longstanding enthusiasm for the potential opportunities for ethnic secessionism in Iran as a means of unseating its current government (Hamid, 2019; Nader and Stewart 2013).

The ethno-religious minorities residing in the three provinces, that are the focus of this paper, being primarily Sunni and either Kurd or Baluch, are also under intense scrutiny from Iran's central government due to their long history of acting as a community base for separatist groups challenging the Islamic Republic. Iran's 'ethnic fringe' has also long provided avenues for hostile powers or secessionist groups based in neighbouring countries, and has thus become highly securitised (Abrahamian 1993, 115-118; Elling 2008, 486).

The constitution of the Islamic Republic contains a number of articles which relate specifically to minorities in Iran, most notably articles 12, 13, 15 and 19.² These articles all allude to some form of protection of rights for minorities, with provision offered in principle for freedom of worship and non-interference in jurisprudential matters for other Muslim sects, official recognition of non-Muslim minorities, and use of non-Persian regional languages. However, only non-Muslim minorities are given explicit political representation in terms of parliament. There are also legal restrictions regarding certain political positions in Iran. These include the stipulation in article 115 that the president must be

a Muslim and 'believe' in the official religion the country (i.e. Shi'ism), thus restricting access to the highest elected role in the country. Ministers are also to be elected from among 'Iranian Muslims,' thus precluding non-Muslim participation in high-ranking government office.³

Overview of Successive Iranian Administrations' Policies Towards Ethno-Religious Minorities

The government's initial phase of ethnic policies spanned from 1979 to 1989. During this time, the government prioritised security, in terms of establishing a secure post-revolutionary regime and managing the eight-year war with Iraq, while policies oriented towards minority groups were pushed to one side. This was seen in an emphasis on bolstering security measures targeted at managing minority populations, rather than concentrating on initiatives related to their economic advancement and the promotion of political involvement. From 1989 to 1997, coinciding with the start of start of Ayatollah Khomeini's leadership, Iran's ethnic policies entered a new phase. Following the war's conclusion, policies aimed at developing the affected and/or neglected regions meant that ethnic minorities became more of a priority. The government shifted its focus from security to economic reform, prioritising the development of the economy and increasing its presence in Iran's 'ethnic fringe.'

During Khatami's presidency (1997-2005), there was a noticeable difference in the government's focus compared to previous periods, with an emphasis on building a more inclusive civil society. Khatami stated that the

² Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran, English version: <https://ecnl.org/sites/default/files/files/2021/IranConstitution.pdf>

³ Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran, English version: <https://ecnl.org/sites/default/files/files/2021/IranConstitution.pdf>

emphasis on quantitative and one-dimensional development, which focuses on economic areas, was unachievable in relation to the ethnic and religious minorities in the border areas of the country and could not solve ‘ethnic problems’ (Ahmadi 2011, 156). The presidency of Mahmoud Ahmadinejad (2005-2013) saw an emphasis on policies aimed at aiding the lower classes, with a strong emphasis on a more Persian and Shi’i-centric national identity, thus alienating some ethno-religious groups.

Conversely, the Rouhani presidency (2013-2021) saw various activities that influenced ethnic trends, including drafting the Charter of Citizen Rights, placing emphasis on Constitution principles 15 and 16 related to minority rights, appointing a special assistant for minority affairs. The ethnic policies during the first term of Ebrahim Raisi (2021-) have thus far been similar to those of Ahmadinejad’s first term, emphasising national (mass) unity and also moving towards a more securitised stance toward Iran’s minority groups.

Overview of Participation Rates in Ethnic Minority Provinces in Presidential Elections

To comprehend the political conduct of Sunnis in elections, the involvement of three Sunni majority provinces of Sistan-Baluchistan (approximately 85% Sunni), Kurdistan (approximately 80% Sunni) and West Azerbaijan (approximately 60% Sunni) are examined in relation to presidential elections in Iran (see work of Soltani 2016; Masaeli 2023 for contemporary population estimates). As an ethnically heterogeneous country, it is not possible to offer an in-depth treatment of all minorities’ experiences with the multiple electoral processes that exist in the Islamic Republic. In addition to the common understanding of Kurdistan and Sistan-Baluchistan being largely distinct in both ethnic and religious terms, it is notable that West Azerbaijan can be seen as Iran’s third Sunni province on account of its large Kurdish population.

The below graphical illustration shows turnout in the three provinces for presidential elections compared to overall turnout.⁴

From the above, one can see that turnout in

⁴ Data is obtained from these websites: <https://irandataportal.syr.edu>, <https://www.moi.ir/service/election-headquarter>. *author's own illustration

Iran's presidential elections differs across the selected provinces and is often at odds with the overall turnout picture for the rest of the country. In the first decades of the Islamic Republic, participation rates in Sunni majority provinces examined here lagged substantially behind the overall turnout. The political atmosphere of the first decade of the Islamic Republic was impacted by the Iran-Iraq war, domestic concerns with regime security, and security incidents in the east and west of Iran, which likely explain the lower participation rates in these provinces, and which are significantly lower than the overall turnout. Participation in these provinces improved from the election of Rafsanjani in 1989, falling more into line with the national average, though remained comparatively low in Sistan-Baluchistan until 1997. This relative uptick in turnout reflects the improved security environment in the country following the cessation of the Iran-Iraq war, as well as the impact of the constitutional amendments enacted following the death of Khomeini, which elevated the status of the presidential office in Iran (Ahmadi 2011, 25-29).

We can see something of a pattern of these provinces often voting for reformist candidates in opposition to the perceived 'establishment' and/or conservative candidate.⁵ Indeed, all reformist candidates have emphasised minority rights in their campaigns, for example Khatami 1997, Mousavi/Karroubi 2009, and Rouhani in 2013/2017 (Rahimikhani, 2020, 99). This was evident in the 1997 election of Khatami, the first round of the 2005 elections, the 2009 elections (with the exception of Kurdistan), in the 2013 victory of Rouhani, and in the 2017 election of Hassan Rouhani against the establishment-supported candidate, and eventual

⁵ See <https://irandataportal.syr.edu/presidential-elections> for individual breakdowns of election turnouts and 'winning candidate per province' information for presidential elections since 1980. A table by the authors collating this information is available on request.

president himself from 2021, Ebrahim Raisi.

In terms of overall turnout, the figures for the election of Khatami in 1997 represent a prominent peak in participation rates in Kurdistan and West Azerbaijan in particular. This is commensurate with what was at the time a record turnout for a presidential election (bettered only by the turnout in the disputed elections of 2009), and a notable moment of change in the political atmosphere of Iran. Though not reaching the same participation rates as the other two provinces, Sistan-Baluchistan's turnout for this election was its highest on record at the time, and participation continued to grow in the province, often exceeding overall voter turnout at successive presidential elections, and regularly topping 70%, with the exception of the 2021 election, in which there was a record low turnout overall at only 48%. It is notable that turnout in Sistan-Baluchistan for the 2021 election was still some 12% higher than the national average. Kurdistan's participation has been lower than other two provinces on average, with a notable dip in 2005 when Ahmadinejad was elected president. This is likely a result of Ahmadinejad's rejection of Kurdish demands during his campaign.

The fact that all three provinces supported the conservative, establishment-backed candidate, Raisi, in the 2021 elections might appear as something of an anomaly. However, this is also due in part to the lack of serious alternative candidates being offered in the presidential race, thus leading to the record low turnout. It can also be seen as a reflection of key Sunni leaders, such as the Baluchi leader Molavi Abdolhamid Ismaeelzahi, offering their support for Raisi in explicit terms, and a wider sense of disillusionment

with the reformist/moderate project in not delivering on the goals it had set for improving minority rights. In interviews with Sunni religious scholars and politicians, the respondents viewed elections as a means of participation rather than a political activity, due to the sensitivity surrounding Sunni leaders.⁶ This sense of political realism stemmed from the perception that Sunnis were unable to become part of the power structure in Iran, due in part to their historical experiences as a minority, and a lack of belief in their ability to attain political power.⁷ As a result, Sunni populations were characterised as preferring social interaction and camaraderie rather than engaging in explicit political action, and can be seen preferring to remain ‘non-political’ in more general terms.⁸

Conclusion

This short intervention has illustrated how the political orientation of Iran’s ethnic and religious minorities can be analysed through their participation rates. The data presented in this paper demonstrates that voter turnout for presidential elections in these three, largely Sunni provinces, that are also distinct in ethnic terms from the majority population of Iran, often lagged behind overall turnout figures in the early years of the revolution. This was influenced by the adverse security situation both in these provinces and in the country as a whole during the war years. Participation rates have tended to peak around the rising popularity of reformist candidates, and the voting choices confirm that support for reformist candidates tends to be more probable. Participation is also influenced by the prominence of local leaders’ engagement with electoral processes, as seen in the compara-

tively high participation rates in Sistan-Baluchistan from the Khatami period onward. ♦

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6 Interview with Sunni religious and political leaders. Names, time and location anonymised due to sensitivity of subject and participants’ need for confidentiality.

7 Ibid

8 Ibid

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